

CLINICAL - NEUROLOGICAL, NEUROIMAGING, AND DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES
OF CALL-FLEMING SYNDROME

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Relevance. Call-Fleming syndrome, or reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome (RCVS), is a relatively uncommon cerebrovascular condition in clinical practice; however, if not diagnosed early, it may lead to severe complications. It is primarily characterized by thunderclap headache, segmental or multifocal narrowing of the intracranial arteries, and regression of these changes over time.

The syndrome is often associated with the postpartum period, vasoactive medications, emotional stress, physical exertion, and other trigger factors. Assessing the clinical-neurological and neuroimaging characteristics of this syndrome, as well as improving the diagnostic approach in local practice, remains highly relevant for practical neurology.

Objective. To evaluate clinical-neurological manifestations, trigger factors, neuroimaging and paraclinical findings, compliance with diagnostic criteria, as well as treatment outcomes and clinical management in patients with Call-Fleming syndrome.

Materials and Methods. This study was conducted as a prospective, single-center, observational cohort investigation. It was carried out during 2023–2025 in the Neurology Departments No. 1 and No. 2 of the clinic of Andijan State Medical Institute. Thirty patients with an established diagnosis of Call-Fleming syndrome or with a strong clinical suspicion of this condition were included. All patients underwent clinical-neurological examination, assessment of anamnestic trigger factors, blood pressure monitoring, laboratory investigations, and neuroimaging studies.

The neuroimaging evaluation included brain MRI/MRA, CT/CT angiography, MR venography when indicated, and cerebrospinal fluid analysis in selected cases. Diagnostic assessment was performed according to the clinical-radiological criteria of Call-Fleming syndrome and the RCVS₂ score. Treatment effectiveness was evaluated based on headache regression, the dynamics of neurological status, and repeated neuroimaging follow-up results.

Results. Among the 30 patients included in the cohort, 23 were women (76.7%) and 7 were men (23.3%). Postpartum women accounted for 9 cases (30.0%). The mean age of the patients was 38.6±9.4 years, with an age range of 22–58 years.

Clinical analysis showed thunderclap headache in 29 patients (96.7%), while recurrent attacks were recorded in 27 patients (90.0%). Nausea and vomiting were observed in 18 cases (60.0%), photophobia and phonophobia in 13 cases (43.3%), focal neurological signs in 9 cases (30.0%), and transient visual disturbances in 6 cases (20.0%).

Trigger factor analysis revealed vasoactive or serotonergic medications in 12 patients (40.0%), making them one of the leading causes. Postpartum and hormonal factors were identified in 9 patients (30.0%), emotional stress and physical exertion in 5 cases each (16.7%), and triggers associated with the Valsalva maneuver or sexual activity in 4 patients (13.3%).

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Neuroimaging evaluation demonstrated segmental or multifocal vasoconstriction in 24 patients (80.0%), confirming this as the major radiological sign. In addition, PRES-related changes were found in 1 patient, convexity subarachnoid hemorrhage in 1 patient, and ischemic lesions in 2 patients. In 3 cases, the initial neuroimaging findings were normal, while vasoconstriction became evident during dynamic follow-up.

In evaluating compliance with diagnostic criteria, 21 patients (70.0%) fully met the criteria, 6 patients (20.0%) partially met them, and 3 patients (10.0%) were classified as suspicious cases. According to the RCVS₂ scoring system, 19 patients had a score of 5 or higher, strongly supporting the diagnosis. Nimodipine was used as the main conservative treatment in 26 patients (86.7%). Verapamil or nifedipine was administered in 4 patients (13.3%), magnesium sulfate in 3 postpartum patients (10.0%), intra-arterial vasodilators in 4 patients (13.3%), and milrinone in 1 patient (3.3%).

During follow-up, most patients demonstrated a reduction in headache attacks, regression of neurological signs, and angiographic confirmation of reversible vasoconstriction.

Discussion. The obtained results showed that Call-Fleming syndrome occurs predominantly in women of reproductive age, especially during the postpartum period. The fact that thunderclap headache was recorded in nearly all patients confirms that it is the main clinical hallmark of this syndrome.

Identification of trigger factors, awareness that the initial neuroimaging study may be normal, and repeated dynamic assessment of patients are of great importance for early diagnosis.

The local observational data are consistent with international findings and demonstrate the practical effectiveness of conservative management based on nimodipine.

Conclusion. In the local cohort, Call-Fleming syndrome was observed mainly in women of reproductive age and postpartum patients. The clinical core of the syndrome consisted of thunderclap headache and its recurrent attacks.

Identification of trigger factors, confirmation of segmental or multifocal vasoconstriction, and dynamic neuroimaging monitoring increase diagnostic reliability. Conservative treatment based on nimodipine, with interventional approaches when necessary, resulted in favorable clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Call-Fleming syndrome, RCVS, thunderclap headache, trigger factors, vasoconstriction, PACNS, PRES, reversibility, postpartum period, nimodipine.

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